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Synthesis of some Substituted-dibenzodiazepinones. A Tricyclic System

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THERE has been some remarkable advances made on seven-membered azepine systems like benzodiazepine¹, dibenzodiazepine² etc. as psychopharmacological agents. This led us to synthesise a few such linearly substituted diazepines.

The substituted dibenzodiazepine (3) was synthesised by reacting 3-(*o*-aminoanilino)-5,5-dimethyl-2-cyclohexen-1-one (2) (2 was obtained by condensation of *o*-phenylenediamine and dimedone) with various substituted thiazole aldehydes (1) followed by *in situ* cyclisation in presence of ethanol containing small amount of acetic acid (Scheme 1). The reactivity of 2 with the aldehyde (1) is attributed to its enaminone structure in which 2-position is reactive towards electrophilic reagents³. The structures of the compounds were confirmed by elemental and spectral data.

Scheme 1

Experimental

4-Chloromethyl-2-(*N*-acetyl-*N*-2,5-dichlorophenyl)thiazole: 2,5-Dichlorophenylthiourea (2 g, 0.009

mol) was treated with 1,3-dichloroacetone (1.2 g, 0.009 mol) in dry acetone for 24 h at room temperature with stirring. The excess acetone was distilled off under reduced pressure. The crude product was treated with acetic anhydride (2.8 g, 0.3 mol) under reflux for 1.5 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and poured into water and extracted with CHCl₃. The chloroform extract was dried (Na₂SO₄), filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure. The gummy residue was passed through silica gel (35 g) column using CHCl₃ as eluant. The resulting solid was crystallised from acetonitrile (70%), m.p. 115°.

4-Formyl-2-(*N*-acetyl-*N*-2,5-dichlorophenyl)thiazole (1): A mixture of 1 (2 g, 0.00596 mol) and hexamethylene tetramine (2.5 g, 0.018 mol) in 50% acetic acid (15 cm³) was refluxed for 1 h at 130°–40°. The reaction mixture was cooled and neutralised with aqueous NaHCO₃ and extracted with CHCl₃. The dried CHCl₃ extract on evaporation yielded a brown oil which was purified over silica gel (30 g) column using CHCl₃ as eluant. The resulting solid was recrystallised from CHCl₃–MeOH (1 : 1), (50%), m.p. 142°; *M*⁺ 316, 318 (due to Cl atoms); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 670, 1 690 (CHO), 1 590 (N–COCH₃) and 1 480 cm⁻¹ (aromatic); δ (CDCl₃) 2.1 (3H, s, N–COCH₃), 7.4 (2H, s, assigned as 'b'), 7.8 (1H, s, assigned as 'a') and 9.7 (1H, s, CHO).

3,3-Dimethyl-2,3,4,4,5,10,11-hexahydro-11-(2-*N*-acetyl-*N*-2,5-dichlorophenylthiazolyl)-1*H*-dibenzo[*b,e*] [1,4]diazepine-1-one (3; R₁=R₃=Cl, R₂=H): To a solution of 2 (1 g, 0.0043 mol) in ethanol were added the aldehyde (1; 1.4 g, 0.00435 mol) and a drop of acetic acid. The solution was refluxed for 1 h and cooled. The resulting solid was crystallised from CHCl₃–MeOH (1 : 1), (54%), m.p. 245°; *M*⁺ 526, 28 (due to Cl atoms); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 290, 3 310 (NH), 1 690 (α,β -unsat. 6-mem. ketone), 1 580, 1 540, 1 500 cm⁻¹ (aromatic); δ (CHCl₃) 1.1 (6H, s, 2×*t*-CH₃), 1.9 (3H, s, N–CO–CH₃), 2.15 (2H, s, CH₂ at C₄), 2.35 (2H, s, CH₂ at C₂), 4.5 (1H, s, NH D₂O exchangeable), 6.2–7.5 (8H, m, ArH), 5.7 (1H, s, NH at 5-position not exchangeable with D₂O due to enaminic NH). Similarly other compounds were prepared (Table 1).

TABLE 1 – PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3*

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅	M.p. **	Yield %
1.	Cl	H	Cl	H	H	245 ^a	54
2.	H	Cl	H	H	H	282 ^b	57
3.	Cl	H	Cl	CH ₃	CH ₃	193 ^c	62
4.	H	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	219 ^b	61
5.	H	CH ₃	H	H	H	120 ^c	70

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

**Solvent for crystallisation: ^aCHCl₃ + MeOH (1 : 1), ^bacetonitrile, ^cethanol.

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**Bridgehead Nitrogen Heterocycles. Part II.
Reactions of 4-Bromo-3-methyl-1-substituted-
5-pyrazolones with 4-Amino-3-mercapto-5-
substituted-*s*-triazoles and Cyclic
Thioureas¹**

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IN view of the physiological activities of triazole derivatives, it was thought of interest to synthesise compounds in which pyrazole ring is fused to other biologically active rings, viz. triazolothiadiazine, imidazothiazoles and its analogs.

4-Bromo-3-methyl-1-substituted-5-pyrazolones (1) exist in the enolic form because the ir spectrum of 1 ($R=H$, C_6H_5) did not display any peak in the carbonyl region, instead there was a broad peak around $3300-3100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (OH). Similar observation has been made in the synthesis of 3-(2-benzothiazolyl)-5-pyrazolones, which were shown to exist in the enolic form as evidenced by the ir and pmr spectral data². Thus 1 on condensation with 4-amino-3-mercapto-5-substituted-*s*-triazoles gave 3-methyl-1,7-disubstituted-pyrazolo [3,4-*e*][3,4-*b*] triazolo-9*H*-1,3,4-thiadiazines hydrobromides (2), which on neutralisation with sodium carbonate solution liberated the free base 3 (Scheme 1). This alternative structure 4 was discarded on the basis of pmr spectral data. If the structure 4 was correct then the methyl protons should have appeared as a doublet due to the presence of hydrogen at the 4-position. However in the pmr spectrum of 3 ($R=C_6H_5$, $R_2=(o)HO-C_6H_4$), the methyl signal at $\delta 2.68$ appeared as a singlet, corroborating the

structure 3. Moreover, the ir spectrum showed a band at 3280 cm^{-1} (NH) (vide experimental).

The reaction of 1 with 2-mercapto-4,5-diphenylimidazole led to the formation of 5 which on treatment with ammonia yielded 3-methyl-1,6,7-triphenylpyrazolo [3,4-*d*][2,1-*b*]imidazothiazole (4; $R_1=C_6H_5$). 3-Methyl-1-substituted-6,7-dihydropyrazolo [3,4-*d*][2,1-*b*]imidazothiazole (7), 3-methyl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydropyrazolo [3,4-*d*]thiazolo [3,2-*a*]pyrimidine (8) and 3-methyl-1-substituted-6,7,8,9-tetrahydropyrazolo [3,4-*d*] [thiazolo [3,2-*a*] [1,3]diazepine (9) hydrobromides were synthesised by the condensation of 1 with 2-mercaptoimidazoline, 2-mercapto-3,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidine and 1*H*-2-mercapto-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro [1,3]diazepine. Similarly, condensation of 1 with 2-mercaptobenzimidazole and neutralisation of the resulting hydrobromide salt afforded 3-methylpyrazolo [3,4-*d*]thiazolo [3,2-*a*]benzimidazole (10; $R_1=H$).

The spectral characteristics of compounds 6, 7 and 10 are consistent with the structures proposed. In the pmr spectra of compounds 3, 6, 7 and 10, the 3-methyl protons were found to resonate downfield around $\delta 2.2-2.6$. This deshielding has its origin in the magnetic anisotropy of the C=N group with little contribution from the rest of the ring.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected and were determined in a sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr/nujol) were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. 5-Alkyl-substituted-4-amino-3-mercapto-*s*-triazoles were prepared by refluxing a mixture of thiocarbonylhydrazide and the corresponding aliphatic acids as described in the literature³. 5-Aryl-4-amino-3-mercapto-*s*-triazoles were synthesised by the reported method⁴. 2-Mercaptoimidazoline, 2-mercapto-3,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidine, 1*H*-2-mercapto-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro [1,3]diazepine and 2-mercaptobenzimidazole were prepared following the literature⁵ methods.

3-Methyl-1-phenyl-7(*o*)-hydroxyphenylpyrazolo [3,4-*e*] [3,4-*b*] triazolo-9*H*-1,3,4-thiadiazines (3; $R_1=C_6H_5$; $R_2=(o)HO-C_6H_4$; 1.26 g, 0.005 mol). 5-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-4-amino-3-mercapto-*s*-triazole¹ (1.04 g, 0.005 mol) and anhydrous ethanol was refluxed on a steam-bath for 15 h. It was then cooled and the resulting solid was washed with ethanol: hydrobromide salt (1.44 g, 65%), m.p. 242° (Found: S, 6.8%. $C_{18}H_{18}N_6SOBr$ requires: S, 7.22%) The hydrobromide salt was dissolved in sodium carbonate solution and the pH was adjusted to 7 with acetic acid to give the free base, m.p. $192-95^\circ$ (aqueous acetic acid) (Found: C, 59.45; H, 3.89; S, 8.57. $C_{18}H_{14}N_6SO$ requires: C, 59.67; H, 3.87; S, 8.84%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3500 (OH), 3280 (NH), 1625 , 1580 (C=C, C=N), 1460 (C-N) and 1375 cm^{-1} (CH deformation in CH_2); δ (TFA)